

******Overview******

This dataset is processed to study time lags between the detection of GNSS signal scintillation at northern auroral latitudes and the onset of fifteen geomagnetic storms that occurred in 2015-2017.

Dataset Description:

- subfolder 'Time lag/2015/IPP120'*
- subfolder 'Time lag/2015/IPP350'*
- subfolder 'Time lag/2016/IPP120'*
- subfolder 'Time lag/2016/IPP350'*
- subfolder 'Time lag/2017/IPP120'*
- subfolder 'Time lag/2017/IPP350'*

The above subfolders contain the files including the time lag data estimated from 13 GNSS sites during 15 geomagnetic storms that commenced in 2015-2017. The datasets are provided with two representative IPP altitudes at 120 km and 350 km. The dataset format is consistent among files. Each column (from left to right) in the file represents:

- Year*
- Day of Year*
- Month*
- Day of Month*
- Hour*
- Minute*
- Second*
- Geomagnetic latitude of IPP in degree*
- Geomagnetic longitude of IPP in degree*
- Heights of IPP in kilometers*
- Geographic latitude of IPP in degree*
- Geographic longitude of IPP in degree*
- Magnetic local time in hours*
- Time lag in minutes*